

Relationships Between Leadership Styles and Internal Social Capital with Organizational Knowledge Sharing

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Abstract

Organizational Knowledge Sharing enables institutions to learn from their own experiences, establish organizational infrastructures, and develop fundamental capabilities to document and share knowledge, address challenges, and model solutions. This research aims to empirically validate a theoretical model that analyzes the relationship between Leadership Styles and Internal Social Capital with Organizational Knowledge Sharing. The study follows a quantitative, non-experimental, cross-sectional, and explanatory research approach, employing structural equation modeling. Data collection relied on a questionnaire using a 7-point Likert scale (1 = never to 7 = always), and a confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to ensure construct validity.

The structural analysis results indicated a well-fitted model, revealing positive relationships among the variables. The study concludes that fostering internal social capital presents an opportunity for institutions to achieve effective organizational knowledge sharing. These findings contribute to managerial education disciplines and internal organizational processes by emphasizing the value of employees' tacit knowledge (know-how) and the management strategies required to strengthen the structural, cognitive, and relational dimensions of internal social capital.

Keywords: Organizational knowledge sharing, transformational leadership, transactional leadership, internal cognitive, social capital, internal relational social capital, internal structural social capital.

Introduction

The most influential scholars in the field of organizational knowledge creation, Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995), introduced the concept of the "spiral of organizational knowledge creation," which delineates four modes of organizational knowledge transfer: combination, externalization, internalization, and socialization. In a more recent contribution, Contreras-Pacheco et al. (2019) developed a model that identifies intrinsic motivation as a key determinant in knowledge collection and dissemination, shaped by the personal values of the knowledge holder.

Specifically, Alonso and Vega (2024) and Hoang and Truong (2021) underscored that the sharing of both tacit and explicit knowledge remains a priority for organizational managers, as it facilitates the achievement of goals with optimal performance. The examination of factors influencing Organizational knowledge sharing (OKS) holds particular significance today, given its direct impact on productivity and the likelihood of organizational survival (Argote et al., 2000). Employee relationships within the knowledge sharing process contribute to fostering a positive work environment (Zapata, 2023). Additionally, facilitating knowledge sharing in areas where access to knowledge remains limited plays a crucial role in driving organizational innovation. Nevertheless, empirical studies identifying specific elements that enhance organizational knowledge sharing (OKS) remain scarce.

In this context, the present study aims to empirically validate a theoretical model that establishes relationships between Leadership Style (LS) and Internal Social Capital (ISC) in OKS. This research formulates the following two hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Internal Social Capital (ISC) exhibits a positive and significant relationship with organizational knowledge sharing.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Leadership Style (LS) exhibits a positive and significant relationship with organizational knowledge sharing.

Literature Review and Hypotheses

The variables examined in this study address intangible aspects of organizations.

Organizational Knowledge Sharing

Scholars have categorized knowledge into two main types: tacit and explicit knowledge (Alavi & Leidner, 2001). Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995) argued that all knowledge originates within individuals (tacit) and, through intentional action, transforms into organizational knowledge (explicit). Hoang and Truong (2021) explained that explicit knowledge becomes evident through documents, reports, and training programs, influencing organizational culture and employee commitment. Tacit knowledge, on the other hand, encompasses individuals' skills, attitudes, perspectives, and experiences. When successfully transferred, tacit knowledge significantly enhances operational performance.

Lin (2007) described knowledge sharing as a socially interactive culture, incorporating employee experiences and competencies across departments or throughout the organization. This process intensifies when stakeholders engage meaningfully in the discussion of complex issues through transparent and innovative knowledge exchange (Noble et al., 2024). Similarly, Lee and Yu (2011) highlighted that intra-organizational knowledge sharing entails transferring or disseminating knowledge among individuals or groups. Matzler and Mueller (2011) further emphasized knowledge sharing as a critical process in establishing competitive advantage within institutions.

Ouakouak and Ouedraogo (2018) explored the influence of organizational commitment and trust on knowledge sharing and on knowledge utilization. Their analysis focused on the relationship between knowledge sharing and its application under determinants such as affective commitment, continuance commitment, personal trust, and professional trust. Additionally, Alavi and Leidner (2001) concluded that the context in which knowledge sharing occurs should fulfill four essential conditions—what initiates it, what interacts, the space, and the shared domain. In this sense, access to alliance-based relationships facilitates knowledge sharing (Silva-Giraldo et al., 2024).

Building upon the insights gathered in the literature review, organizational knowledge sharing can be defined as a formal, informal, and reciprocal process of transferring employee knowledge within the organization, encompassing both tacit and explicit dimensions.

As a public organization, an educational institution generates both tacit and explicit knowledge with the aim of fostering national or regional development, based on its educational organizational structure.

Internal Social Capital

Several scholars have underscored that social capital originates from the bonds developed both within and beyond organizational boundaries. Discussing social capital involves examining the quality and intensity of relationships (Castillo et al., 2013; Fernández et al., 2005; Gordon, 2005; Juárez et al., 2019; Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998; Urhan et al., 2024; Vargas, 2002). Other researchers have revisited studies on social capital, highlighting its value in organizational management, particularly as a mechanism for learning from past mistakes (Lazkano et al., 2005; Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998).

Juárez et al. (2019) further noted that social capital largely determines economic success; however, no universally accepted definition or accurate measurement tool currently exists. El CSI permite establecer criterios para sumar productos de las relaciones en la red interna de la organización de manera informal, a través de normas, valores y relaciones personales que son parte vital del proceso productivo (Baro, 2012).

Internal Social Capital (ISC) enables the establishment of criteria to account for the intangible outputs generated through internal organizational relationships. These outputs emerge informally through norms, values, and personal interactions that play a vital role in productive processes (Baro, 2012).

Social attitudes such as cooperation and participation prove essential for effective organizational functioning (Boso et al., 2024; Hanifan, 1916; Soares et al., 2024). According to Terrén (2004), ISC facilitates organizational responsiveness to complexity and adds substantial value to internal social interactions. These interactions lay the foundation for social environments that increase an organization's ability to implement initiatives that drive project success.

ISC consists of three dimensions: structural attributes, observable in social networks and patterns of interaction; relational attributes, reflected in the level of trust developed between social entities through ongoing relationships (including trust, shared norms, and mutual obligations); and cognitive attributes, which encompass shared values, goals, and visions among institutional members (Hoang & Truong, 2021).

Thus, ISC may be understood as a feature inherent to individuals or social organizations, involving network connections, norms, and trust that collectively foster organizational coordination and collaboration. Medina (2017) elaborated on the relational, cognitive, and structural dimensions of ISC, asserting their interdependence and their mediating role—particularly in the knowledge-sharing process. Terry et al. (2013) emphasized that all ISC dimensions (relational, cognitive, and structural) exhibit strong associations with organizational knowledge sharing, with cognitive social capital exerting the most substantial influence.

Based on the theoretical contributions reviewed, the authors proposed the following hypothesis: Hypothesis One (H1): Internal Social Capital (ISC) exhibits a positive and significant relationship with Organizational Knowledge Sharing (OKS).

Leadership Style

Galton (2000) documented leadership capabilities within a finite timeframe, categorizing leadership by asserting that "leaders are born." This statement marked a turning point and laid the foundation for trait-based leadership theory. Mendoza et al. (2012) analyzed the influence of transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership on organizational satisfaction among academic and administrative staff in a public upper-secondary education institution, applying Avolio and Bass's (2004) model. The foundational concepts of transformational and transactional leadership initially emerged from the work of Burns (1978).

Cartwright and Zander (1971) defined Leadership Style (LS) as the ability to exercise personal and social power, translating intention into sustained outcomes. Aguirre and Villarreal (2012) described LS as an interactive process wherein leaders direct, advise, guide, and influence their followers. Martínez (2020) similarly characterized LS as an individual's capacity to influence a group toward achieving a vision or a set of goals through ongoing interaction, where the leader assumes the role of advisor and guide.

Robbins and Judge (2009) concurred, identifying leadership as the ability to influence a group toward goal achievement. In line with this, Carranza et al. (2011) emphasized that LS functions as a social process in which a group or organizational member shapes the interpretation of internal and external events, the selection of desired goals, the structuring of work activities, individual motivation, relational power, and shared orientations.

A transactional leadership style operates through exchanges and fulfillment of assigned tasks aligned with monitored objectives, employing control mechanisms to ensure goal attainment within a climate of respect and tolerance (Álamo & Falla, 2023). Within this style, leaders specify roles and expectations for various actors and offer material or psychological rewards based on the fulfillment of contractual responsibilities (Martínez, 2020). Additionally, leaders enforce adherence to established rules (Bass, 1988). Weber's (1947) studies generalized that charisma constitutes a common feature in this style, enabling the leader to transform the group's social environment.

Transactional leaders reward employees for meeting performance standards (Vidales et al., 2023). Effective leaders often display both transactional and transformational traits, albeit in varying degrees (Avolio & Bass, 1995; Bass & Avolio, 1993, 1994, as cited in Avolio et al., 1999). Transformational leadership emphasizes efficiency (Domínguez et al., 2023). Masa'deh et al. (2016) identified a positive relationship between transactional leadership and knowledge sharing. Likewise, Durán and Castañeda (2015) found a significant correlation between transactional leadership and knowledge sharing, while identifying a non-significant correlation in the case of transformational leadership.

Drawing from these theoretical insights, the following hypothesis emerges:

Hypothesis Two (H2): Leadership Style exhibits a positive and significant relationship with Organizational Knowledge Sharing (OKS).

In alignment with both hypotheses and the reviewed literature, the theoretical model for this study has been constructed (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Design of the Theoretical Model of the Relationships between Leadership Styles and Internal Social Capital with Organizational Knowledge Sharing.

Note. Own elaboration based on Avolio & Bass (2004), Hoang & Truong (2021), Martínez (2020), and Robbins & Judge (2009).

Methodology

Type of research

This study followed a non-experimental, cross-sectional, and explanatory design (Hernández-Sampieri & Mendoza, 2018), employing structural equation modeling (SEM) for data analysis.

Object of Study

According to Morán and Alvarado (2010), a conceptually defined variable plays a crucial role in guiding the research process. In this study, three variables were examined (see Table 1).

Table 1: *Conceptualization of the Variables: Leadership Styles, Internal Social Capital, and Organizational Knowledge Sharing*

Variable	Construct
OKS	A bidirectional, formal and informal process of transferring employees' knowledge within the organization, encompassing both the tacit dimension (individual knowledge) and the explicit dimension (organizational knowledge) (Hoang & Truong, 2021).
ISC	Characteristics of individuals or social organizations—such as network connections, shared norms, and trust—that facilitate coordination and collaboration within the organization for mutual benefit (Hoang & Truong, 2021).
LS	An individual's capacity to influence a group of people in order to achieve a vision or set of goals, through an interactive process in which the leader directs, advises, guides, and influences followers (Aguirre & Villarreal, 2012; Martínez, 2020; Robbins & Judge, 2009).

Note. Own elaboration based on Aguirre & Villarreal (2012), Hoang & Truong (2021), Martínez (2020), and Robbins & Judge (2009).

Study Population

The target population consisted of 1,041 employees, categorized as administrative and teaching staff from an upper-secondary education institution in the state of Tabasco, Mexico. The study employed a non-probabilistic sampling method (Kerlinger & Lee, 2002), and the inclusion criterion required participants to hold a permanent contract. To administer the questionnaires, authorization was obtained from the academic director of the educational subsystem, and data collection took place through face-to-face surveys involving 296 employees.

Demographic traits serve as descriptors of the sample. This study considered four characteristics: gender, educational attainment, occupational role, and age range. Among the respondents, 113 were male (39%) and 180 were female (61%). Regarding educational level, the results indicated that seven employees held at least a secondary school diploma (2%), 40 had completed high school (16%), 149 possessed a bachelor's degree (51%), and 90 held a graduate degree (31%).

Of the total sample, 176 participants reported administrative duties (60%), while 117 engaged in teaching activities (40%).

In terms of age distribution, six employees fell within the 18–25 age range (2%), 51 within 26–30 years (17%), 143 within 31–40 years (49%), 78 within 41–50 years (27%), and 15 within 51–60 years (5%).

Measurements

A 52-item questionnaire was developed using a 7-point Likert scale (1 = never to 7 = always). The instrument drew upon previously validated scales published in peer-reviewed scientific articles and subjected to factorial analysis. Table 2 presents the item distribution within the instrument.

Table 2. *Structure of the Measurement Instrument for the Relationships between Leadership and Internal Social Capital with Organizational Knowledge Sharing*

Dimension	Item	Author
Organizational Knowledge Sharing (OKS)	1. Openness in communication and frequent knowledge sharing among institutional members proves useful for my work tasks.	Kang et al. (2008)
	2. The knowledge I acquire through my work remains well-organized for sharing.	Kang et al. (2008)
	3. The knowledge I acquire through my work can be easily understood and shared.	Kang et al. (2008)
	4. The knowledge I gain on the job contributes to better performance.	Kang et al. (2008)
	5. The knowledge I gain on the job proves adequate for improved performance.	Kang et al. (2008)
	6. The knowledge I acquire proves effective in improving problem-solving.	Kang et al. (2008)
	7. Openness in communication and frequent knowledge sharing among institutional members contributes positively to my work tasks.	Kang et al. (2008)
	8. The knowledge I acquire remains well-organized for dissemination.	Kang et al. (2008)
	9. The knowledge I acquire can be clearly understood for sharing purposes.	Kang et al. (2008)
	10. The knowledge I gain on the job supports improved work performance.	Kang et al. (2008)
	11. The knowledge I gain proves suitable for enhanced job performance.	Kang et al. (2008)
	12. The knowledge I acquire helps improve problem-solving effectiveness.	Kang et al. (2008)
Internal Social Capital (ISC)	13. My colleagues and I share the same vision and goals.	Hoang & Truong (2021)
	14. My colleagues and I understand the strategic goals of the institution.	Castillo et al. (2013)
	15. My colleagues and I recognize the institution's direction and working style.	Castillo et al. (2013)
	16. I can rely on my colleagues when needed.	Hoang & Truong (2021)
	17. Colleagues support one another in developing new ideas and enhancing job capacity.	Hoang & Truong (2021)

Dimension	Item	Author
Transformational Leadership Style (LS)	18. Colleagues collaborate to generate new ideas and build capacity in daily work.	Castillo et al. (2013)
	19. I maintain a positive relationship with my colleagues.	Hoang & Truong (2021)
	20. My coworkers recognize my skills, knowledge, or competencies.	Hoang & Truong (2021)
	21. I remain aware of which of my skills, knowledge, or competencies could be useful to my coworkers.	Hoang & Truong (2021)
	22. My department functions as a team where mutual trust exists.	Castillo et al. (2013)
	23. In my institution, colleagues engage informally to share ideas and information about daily tasks.	Delgado-Verde et al. (2011)
	24. In my institution, colleagues engage in constructive discussions when issues arise.	Delgado-Verde et al. (2011)
	25. I feel proud to work with my immediate supervisor.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	26. My immediate supervisor sacrifices personal interests for the benefit of others.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	27. My immediate supervisor acts in a way that earns my respect.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	28. My supervisor conveys authority and confidence.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	29. My supervisor talks about their most important values and beliefs.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	30. My supervisor inspires others to aspire to greater goals.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	31. My supervisor considers the ethical and moral consequences of their actions.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	32. My supervisor explains the importance of having a team mission.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	33. My immediate supervisor speaks optimistically about the future.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	34. My immediate supervisor speaks enthusiastically about what must be done to reach goals.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	35. My immediate supervisor presents a positive vision of the future.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	36. My immediate supervisor expresses confidence in goal achievement.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	37. My supervisor evaluates problem-solving approaches to ensure their appropriateness.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	38. My supervisor seeks alternative ways to resolve problems.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
39. My supervisor encourages others to view problems from various perspectives.	Bass & Avolio (2004)	
40. My supervisor proposes new methods for completing tasks.	Bass & Avolio (2004)	
41. My supervisor spends time teaching or coaching subordinates.	Bass & Avolio (2004)	

Dimension	Item	Author
Transactional Leadership Style (LS)	42. My supervisor treats others as individuals, not merely as employees.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	43. My immediate supervisor recognizes that each person has different needs, abilities, and aspirations.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	44. My immediate supervisor helps others develop their strengths.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	45. My immediate supervisor helps or supports others in giving their best effort.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	46. My supervisor clearly defines who is responsible for specific tasks.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	47. My supervisor recognizes others when they achieve goals.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	48. My supervisor expresses satisfaction when goals are achieved.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	49. My supervisor focuses attention on irregularities, errors, or anything out of the ordinary.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	50. My supervisor focuses on resolving problems, complaints, and failures.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
	51. My supervisor monitors errors efficiently.	Bass & Avolio (2004)
52. My supervisor directs attention to mistakes in order to achieve goals.	Bass & Avolio (2004)	

Note. Adapted from Bass & Avolio (2004); Castillo et al. (2013); Delgado-Verde et al. (2011); Hoang & Truong (2021); Kang et al. (2008).

Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to assess the construct validity of the scales, using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0.0 (SPSS) and IBM SPSS Amos version 24.0.0 (AMOS). The analysis began with verification of assumptions for multivariate analysis. Data normality was evaluated using Mardia’s coefficient, which reported a multivariate kurtosis value of 90.29—considered acceptable for normality (Valdés et al., 2020). To demonstrate homoscedasticity, the authors applied Levene’s test. The analysis, conducted in SPSS, yielded values ranging from 0.131 to 0.666, indicating insufficient statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, the data were considered homoscedastic in most items, confirming the presence of equal variances.

To verify collinearity, linear regression was performed using collinearity statistics—specifically, tolerance and the variance inflation factor (VIF). The VIF ranged from 1.501 to 7.641, indicating that 100% of the items did not exhibit multicollinearity.

Residual independence was assessed via linear regression in SPSS, using the Durbin-Watson statistic, which yielded a value of 2.132. This result suggested that residuals were independent.

The model fit indices for the three scales demonstrated excellent adjustment (see Table 3), and all estimated parameters proved highly significant (see Table 4).

Table 3. *Fit Indices by Scale for Leadership Styles, Internal Social Capital, and Organizational Knowledge Sharing*

Fit Indicators	ISC	OKS	Transformational LS	Transactional LS
Chi-square	82.26	22.14	142.18	24.70
Degrees of freedom	41.00	19.00	80.00	13.00
Discrepancy ratio (CMIN/DF)	2.01	1.17	1.77	1.90
Fit Measures				
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	.10	.05	.04	.03
Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI)	.95	.98	.94	.98
Comparative Measures				
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	.97	.99	.96	.98
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	.06	.02	.05	.06

Note. Acceptable thresholds: SRMR < 0.080 (Hu & Bentler, 1999); GFI > 0.90; CFI > 0.95; RMSEA < 0.06 (Valdés et al., 2020). Evaluation standards: CMIN/DF > 5 = Poor; > 3 = Acceptable; > 1 = Excellent; CFI < .90 = Poor; < .95 = Acceptable; > .95 = Excellent; SRMR > .10 = Poor; > .08 = Acceptable; < .08 = Excellent; RMSEA > .08 = Poor; > .06 = Acceptable; < .06 = Excellent (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Table 4. *Estimated Parameters of the Model for Leadership Styles, Internal Social Capital, and Organizational Knowledge Sharing*

Variable	Observed	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	Standard deviation	z	p
OKS	ICOEX04	1.00	0,91			
	ICOEX05	1.04	0,95	0,04	28,99	***
	ICOEX06	0,98	0,93	0,04	27.04	***
	ICOTA03	1.00	0,63			
	ICOTA04	1.36	0,85	0,12	11.37	***
	ICOTA05	1.39	0,87	0,12	11.45	***
	ICOTA06	1.19	0,75	0,12	10.42	***
	ICOEX01	0,67	0,63	0,05	12.56	***
ISC	CSIES03	1.00	0,50			
	CSIES04	1,72	0,61	0,26	6.69	***
	CSIES05	1,80	0,67	0,26	6,98	***
	CSIES06	2.21	0.69	0.31	7.06	***
	CSIRE02	1.00	0.61			
	CSIRE01	1.68	0.97	0.15	11.35	***
	CSIRE03	1.23	0.78	0.11	10.81	***
	CSICO01	1.00	0.69			
	CSICO02	1.11	0.89	0.08	13.30	***
	CSICO03	1.08	0.87	0.08	13.14	***
Transformational LS	LITFIIC02	1.00	0.70			
	LITFIIC04	1.00	0.69	0.10	9.80	***

Variable	Observed	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	Standard deviation	z	p
	LITFIM01	1.00	0.68			
	LITFIM02	1.04	0.78	0.09	11.04	***
	LITFIM03	1.00	0.74	0.09	10.66	***
	LITFIM04	0.92	0.71	0.09	10.32	***
	LITFEI02	1.00	0.59			
	LITFEI03	1.42	0.78	0.17	8.49	***
	LITFEI04	1.21	0.66	0.15	8.01	***
	LITFIIA01	1.00	0.70			
	LITFIIA04	1.13	0.70	0.13	8.93	***
	LITFIIA02	0.65	0.43	0.11	6.13	***
	LITFIIC01	0.91	0.58	0.11	8.40	***
Transactional LS	LITSPC01	1.00	0.65			
	LITSPC02	1.06	0.69	0.14	7.51	***
	LITSPC03	1.06	0.60	0.15	7.21	***
	LITSAEA01	1.00	0.71			
	LITSAEA02	1.08	0.79	0.10	11.19	***
	LITSAEA03	0.93	0.70	0.09	10.26	***
	LITSAEA04	0.96	0.69	0.10	10.10	***

Note. Field Data Obtained through AMOS.

*** p < 0,001) (Gaskin et al., 2019).

To assess the reliability of the scales, Composite Reliability (CR), McDonald's Omega (Ω), and Cronbach's Alpha (α) were calculated. According to Hair et al. (2010), McDonald's Omega (Ω) represents the extent to which observed constructs consistently measure the latent construct, with a recommended threshold of ≥ 0.60 . In this study, all values exceeded the minimum recommended threshold, demonstrating the reliability of the scales. Cronbach's Alpha coefficients were above .77, further confirming the consistency of the reliability measures (see Table 5).

Table 5. Reliability of the Scales: Leadership Styles, Internal Social Capital, and Organizational Knowledge Sharing

Constructs	CR = McDonald's Omega (Ω)	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
Explicit	.92	.91
Tacit	.86	.81
Cognitive	.86	.85
Relational	.84	.81
Structural	.71	.77
Transformational	.87	.90
Transactional	.80	.80

Note. Own elaboration based on field data obtained using AMOS.

Tabla 6. *Fit Indices for the SEM Model Design: Relationships between Leadership Styles, Internal Social Capital, and Organizational Knowledge Sharing*

From Data to Model	Structural Model Design
Chi-square (CMIN)	886.63
Degrees of freedom (DF)	579
Discrepancy ratio (CMIN/DF)	1.53
Fit Measures	
Root Mean Square Residual (RMR)	.13
Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI)	.86
Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index (AGFI)	.84
Parsimonious Goodness-of-Fit Index (PGFI)	.75
Comparative Fit Measures	
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	.83
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	.81
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	.93
Tucker–Lewis Index (TLI/NNFI)	.93
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	.93
Parsimony Fit Measures	
Parsimony Ratio	.92
Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	.76
Parsimonious Comparative Fit Index (PCFI)	.86
Population Discrepancy Measures	
Non-Centrality Parameter	307.64
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	.04

Note. Acceptable thresholds: SRMR < 0.080 (Hu & Bentler, 1999); GFI > 0.90; CFI > .95; RMSEA < .06 (Valdés et al., 2020). Interpretation standards: CMIN/DF > 5 = Poor; > 3 = Acceptable; > 1 = Excellent; CFI < .90 = Poor; < .95 = Acceptable; > .95 = Excellent; SRMR > .10 = Poor; > .08 = Acceptable; < .08 = Excellent; RMSEA > .08 = Poor; > .06 = Acceptable; < .06 = Excellent (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Discussion

According to Medina (2017), the importance of Organizational Knowledge Sharing (OKS) lies in its contribution to the innovation process, the reduction of product and service-related costs, and the creation of mechanisms that facilitate knowledge sharing within the organization. OKS also enables the effective use and generation of new knowledge, while strengthening top management’s decision-making.

The findings of this study support the empirical relationships between Leadership Style (LS) and Internal Social Capital (ISC) with OKS. However, ISC demonstrated a stronger influence on OKS. The results suggest that when employees trust their colleagues in times of need, support one another in developing new ideas, and engage in positive interpersonal relationships,

knowledge sharing is enhanced. Employees who remain aware of their own skills, knowledge, and competencies, and who contribute to informal relationships and engage in constructive dialogue during setbacks, play a significant role in strengthening tacit OKS and contribute even more intensively to explicit OKS.

These results confirm Medina's (2017) findings, which established a close connection between ISC and the knowledge-sharing process. The results also corroborate the studies by Hoang and Truong (2021) and Terry et al. (2013), who emphasized that all dimensions of ISC (i.e., relational, cognitive, and structural) are associated with OKS.

Furthermore, the results validate the study by Masa'deh et al. (2016), which identified a positive relationship between transactional LS and OKS. However, in the present study, although the relationship was positive, it did not reach statistical significance. This contradicts the findings of Durán and Castañeda (2015), who reported a significant correlation between transactional LS and OKS. Given the divergence in results, further research is required to clarify and confirm the contribution of LS to OKS.

Likewise, the findings are consistent with those of Durán and Castañeda (2015), who reported a non-significant correlation between transformational LS and OKS.

Conclusion

This study focused solely on a single academic level of education. Including other educational levels may yield different results and impacts.

An opportunity for institutions to achieve effective organizational knowledge sharing lies in the consolidation of ISC—particularly when shared goals, mutual understanding in formal and informal social networks, goodwill in workplace relationships, norms, and trust enable coordination and collaboration within the organization. These findings provide valuable insights for disciplines related to managerial training and internal organizational processes, emphasizing the value of employee know-how (tacit knowledge) and the importance of managing and strengthening the structural, cognitive, and relational dimensions of ISC.

This research offers reliable and valid measurement scales for assessing institutional efforts in OKS, ISC development, and identification of prevailing LS types. These scales may also serve as references for future empirical studies on these constructs. Further research should explore OKS models that integrate additional variables, investigate the direct relationship between ISC and LS, and apply the measurement instrument across educational institutions at basic and higher education levels to contrast outcomes and relationships.

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